
THE IMAGE OF HUMAN SPIRIT IN OYBEK'S CREATION

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Annotation.

It is known that during the years of independence, the attention to the reformation and renewal of our spiritual life became stronger. Now the restoration of our spiritual, literary, and religious values and directing it to the perfection of a mature person in all respects has risen to the level of state policy. At one of those times, the work of the great Adip Oybek, who enriched our literature, was also looked at. In this article, we will talk about the depiction of the human psyche in Oybek's works.

Introduction

It is no secret that the creative growth of Oybek, who left his name as an indelible mark, was not easy. The poet experienced a period of complex creative growth and research in his youth. Referring to these ups and downs in his creative path, Oybek said: "There were still many contradictions and searches in my first poems. Along with the poems created in response to the most important events of the time... there were also poems written in the spirit of depression, abstracted, filled with a mournful cry," he wrote. The poet's poems such as "Autumn and Girl", "Winter Nights", "Traces from Memory", "Evening of Ferghana", "Separation and Dervish", "For the East", "Uzbek People" were written in the spirit of depression. is one of the works. The meeting of signs of mourning in them is a unique expression of protest against the injustice and social injustice that existed in the life of that time. From his youth, Oybek followed the path of writing the truth and truthfully reflecting the people's spirit. Oybek firmly connects his fate with the fate of the people, constantly searches, studies life carefully.

Main Part

In the program of general education schools of our country, Oybek's novel "Good Blood" is studied. Information about the life and work of Oybek will be given. The history of the creation of the novel "Kutlug Khan", the system of images in the novel, and the artistic embodiment of the characteristics of the image of the

human psyche in the characters of Yolchi and Gulnor are given. In the characters of Yolchi and Mirzakarimboy in the novel, a different mental image can be observed. The artistic value of the novel is analyzed, and the writer's skills in creating an image and creating a composition of the work are studied. Some chapters from the novel "Kutlug Khan" are presented in the 9th grade textbook of general education schools. Speaking about the image of the human psyche in Oybek's works, the image of the human psyche is also shown in the characters of the writer's novel "Navoiy".

Of course, the novel "Navoiy" is a vivid example of such skill. In the novel, Aibek used the image of Navoiy's attitude to the Turkish language and literature in order to create the image of a great poet. As Haqqani describes in the novel, Navoi loves his mother tongue - Turkish. But in the novel, Alisher Navoi rightly points out that he did not discriminate against other languages. In the novel, Navoi objected to the poet Binoy: "We have never denied the power and importance of the Persian language, the beauty and goodness of the works in that language. We have been writing in Persian since childhood. But the advantage of our language is a great truth for us. We cherished the love of this truth in our hearts, we will keep this love until we die! We have clans and clans that fill cities, villages, deserts and mountains, and they have their own pleasure and understanding. Let us think of the pleasure and nature of our country and write in its own language so that its heart is filled with the flowers of thought. Let's sing praises with Turkana words, let the hearts of the people rise. Let our country enjoy the flower of words along with other countries"⁴, he says. The author describes with fascination that Jami and Navoi are each other's teacher and student. Simple human relationships between lifetimes are expressed with sincerity. Before leaving for Marv, Navoi visits Jami with the intention of saying goodbye: "Jami welcomes him with enthusiasm as always. The old man (Jomjy), who was still sitting Navoi, smiled politely and said with his own gentleness: "Will you now turn our eyes to Marv?"⁵. , we can feel the sophistication. Aibek skillfully showed the creative process of the poet.

He tried to describe Navoi's hardships in the process of writing "Khamsa", as well as how his other works came to the world. Navoi's attitude towards religion is also reflected in the work. The dream of the great thinker to go on a pilgrimage is so beautifully expressed in the work that you will be surprised to read it, but this dream will remain a dream for Navoi. Before that, the appointment of the poet as the governor of Astrabad caused him to distance himself from his friends, people of

science, and homesickness. At that time, Navoi feels longing and writes the following rubai: A stranger in a foreign land cannot be happy, El anga shafigu cannot be kind, A golden cage cannot be filled with a red flower, a nightingale cannot be as thorny as a thorn. . In the play, Oybek showed true patriotism through the character of Navoi. Also, the injustices that took place in Herat and Khurasan during the time of the Timurid prince Husayn Baigaro, the conflicts between father and son, the murder of Momin Mirza, the struggle for the throne, and the relentless search for the betterment of the people are clearly described.

In his works, Oybek describes the spiritual experiences of a person in an abstract, sometimes overt way. It embodies the reality of the conflict between people. It is an honor for every person to feel sorry for poor people, show them kindness, and help them as much as they can. Abdulla Qahhor created unique works in accordance with the ideas of humanitarianism put forward by great artists and was able to fully demonstrate his skillful storytelling in Uzbek literature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that Oybek made a blessed contribution to raising the prestige of our literature to the world level with his exemplary life and aspirations, fruitful and effective creative heritage. The creative heritage of the great academic poet, novelist, literary critic and translator Oybek is a part of our culture and literature, and many studies have been conducted to study his work. But today it is extremely important to know and research the creative heritage of the great poet. That is why it is necessary to analyze each of his works based on new views and teach them to young students in order to go deeper into the work of the poet, to illuminate the unique aspects of his works, to learn about his artistic skills.

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